

SCHOOLS AND MADRASAS IN THE PERIOD OF THE RUSSIAN EMPIRE

(in the case of Syrdarya region)

Shahnoza Sharipova

Master's student of the Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Annotation. In work are researched questions of the condition of the schools and madrassa in Syrdarya region after conquest Turkestana Tsarist Russia, social-economic conditions, taught sciences, attitude to colonial administration to sphere of the enlightenment.

Keywords: tsarism, schools, madrassa, scholastic process, study of the sciences, level to literacy, amount of the schools and madrassa.

By the second half of the XIX century, long-term wars, political, military, ideological and economic pressure had yielded results, and Turkestan became completely dependent on the Russian Empire. After the conquest of Turkestan by the Russian Empire, attention was paid primarily to the country's educational system.

During this period, many schools, madrassas and dormitories operated in Turkestan, where educational activities were conducted in a peculiar way. For example, Russians who took their first step into this country were surprised by the literacy of the country's residents and the level of enthusiasm for education here.

Also officials of the empire K.K.Palen, V.P. Nalivkin, D.M. Gramenitsky, N.P. Ostroumov, N.I. Ilminsky, K.E. Based on the information provided by Bendrikov and others, as well as the data presented in some archival materials, the total number of all schools and madrasas in Turkestan region before 1908 can be shown in the following table.

Regions	Schools	Madrasah
Syrdarya region	804	44
Fergana region	2 316	176
Samarkand region	2300	38
Yettisu region	147	10
Total until January 1909	5565	266

As can be seen from the figures in the table, the number of national schools in the provinces of Turkestan prevails in comparison with madrassas. This situation indicates that serious changes are taking place in the education of Turkestan, despite the years of tyranny. [1, P.121-172].

In Turkestan, by 1890, a special 3rd inspector post was established for departmental control of schools. Since 1896, schools and madrassas have been under the jurisdiction of the head of the city and county. In the early 1890s, P. Nalivkin worked as a state inspector of Muslim schools and madrassas of the country. According to him, although the number of schools in the country is officially set at 5 thousand, P. Nalivkin Himself believed that there should be more than twice as many local schools [2, P.775].

In the certificate sent by him to the Ministry of Education on May 8, 1896, the following lines were written: "I consider it necessary to inform you that at present higher schools and madrassas in the Turkestan region are under the supervision of the 3rd inspector of state educational institutions. Junior schools are outside the supervision of this inspector, and it was not possible to obtain their full number due to their extremely large number, therefore there is no official information about the number of schools in the inspection work entrusted to me. Despite this, based on the unofficial information I have, I consider it permissible to state that the total number of schools in the country, including schools of the surplus population in villages, exceeds 5,000" [3, P.775].

It can be noted that in addition to the madrassas founded in the ancient Middle Ages, there is some evidence in the country that new madrassas were built and put into operation on the eve of the occupation of the imperial government and during the occupation not faded. K.E. Bendrikov's information about this can fully substantiate our opinion. Three madrassas were opened in the Oblivsky parish of the Syrdarya region in 1848, in Boka in 1863-1870 and in Zangiot from 1835 to 1950. In 1875 in Shymkent uyezd, in 1840 in the village of Kultepa in Tashkent uyezd, in Piskent and in Turkestan in 1821 and 1875, and in Chinoza in 1874-1878, new madrassas began to operate [4, P.75]. In their works, these authors presented certain data on the economic savings, income and endowment properties of madrasahs, and based on these opinions, one can judge the achievements and shortcomings of a particular madrasah, as well as the level of quality of pedagogical work. determined. If the madrasah has a large income, it means that the educational process has been adjusted and organizational issues have been resolved correctly. The most important thing is that the wealthy part of the people, in addition to sending their children to education, donated their personal income to such madrassas that came to the attention of the population. Count K.K. Palen's information deserves attention. If you look at pages 120-121 of his audit reports, you will see clear and convincing data about these problems and the material condition of the madrasah. In it, the author provides the following information. The total number of madrasahs in the Syrdarya region is 32, of which 23 are located in cities and 9 in villages. The income of these madrasahs from donation property is not very large, but the richest madrasah of Khoja Ahrar in Tashkent has an annual income of 3,100 soums. Another 3 madrassas have an income of 1000-2000 soums, and the rest have a daily income set at 100-10 soums. Some madrasahs do not receive any benefit at all. In conclusion, we can say that the education system in Turkestan, which is the main link of the ancient Turks, has a long history and rich experience, and even the imperial authorities rightly recognized its superiority over the education system in the central regions of Turkestan. But reforming

school and madrasah education in accordance with the times was a requirement of the time. Here it is necessary to recognize that the education system of Turkestan has not been developed based on the requirements of world development, and advanced traditions have not been fully mastered.

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